

The Effectiveness of Project-Based Learning in Developing Students' Critical Thinking Skills

By :

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Abstract :

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is a learning model considered capable of addressing the demands of 21st-century education, particularly in developing students' critical thinking skills. The importance of implementing this model highlights the need for a comprehensive review of its effectiveness. The main problem examined in this study concerns how PjBL is implemented in learning contexts and the extent to which it influences students' critical thinking abilities. In addition, this research investigates the factors that determine the success of PjBL in enhancing student engagement and analytical skills. The research method employs a descriptive survey approach with systematic stages, including determining research objectives, selecting databases, using relevant keywords, screening articles based on inclusion criteria, and conducting content analysis. Articles were collected from ERIC, Harzing Publish or Perish, and Google Scholar, with publication years limited to 2017–2022. The findings indicate that PjBL consistently has a positive impact on improving critical thinking skills through project activities that encourage students to analyze, evaluate, and solve problems independently. Furthermore, the analyzed studies reveal that the success of PjBL is strongly influenced by the teacher's role as a facilitator and the quality of the project design provided.

Keywords : *PjBL, Critical, Students, Analysis, Journal*

Introduction

In the 21st-century learning focuses on mastering academic content while helping students acquire a range of essential skills. Students are encouraged to explore learning content in depth through carefully designed projects. These projects involve investigating questions, discovering solutions, and creating products that demonstrate their understanding. Through this process, students develop critical thinking, collaboration, communication, and problem-solving skills in creative ways. Twenty-first-century skills—such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication—are essential for preparation for higher education and careers, as they help students address real-world problems. Creativity is regarded as a key asset for students' academic success. Kartiningrum (2015) defines creativity as the ability to generate new ideas or concepts that can be used to solve problems

or discover new connections among existing ideas. Student creativity does not always have to involve creating something entirely new; it may also take the form of combining existing ideas to produce something unique. This can be observed through their creative behaviors or activities (Rizkiana et al., 2023).

Furthermore, creative thinking ability is an important component of the skills required in 21st-century learning. This ability includes the capacity to consider multiple possibilities, adopt diverse approaches and perspectives, and generate new ideas. These abilities can guide the creation and selection of alternative solutions. The characteristics of creative thinking can be measured through fluency, flexibility, and originality. Fluency is reflected in the number of ideas generated in response to a prompt or problem. Flexibility is shown by changes in approach when responding to a given task. Originality is reflected in the novelty of the ideas presented as responses to a particular requirement. This view is supported by Silver et al. (1996), who characterize creative skills in terms of fluency (the number of problems posed), flexibility (the types of problems created), and originality (the degree of variation in responses within a set of answers) (Rizkiana et al., 2023).

In addition to creative thinking skills, the framework of 21st-century learning requires students to master skills, knowledge, and expertise in technology, media, and information. They also need learning, innovation, technical, life, and career skills. These competencies are crucial for students to succeed in life and work amid rapid change. The 21st century is characterized by the abundance of information and its widespread dissemination through computers, the automation of routine tasks, and communication that can occur from anywhere. These conditions affect various aspects of life, including education. Therefore, learning approaches are needed that not only emphasize theory but also provide learning experiences that stimulate creativity and problem-solving (Fitriana, 2024).

One approach that aligns with these needs is Project-Based Learning (PjBL). PjBL facilitates students' understanding of subject matter through hands-on practice beyond theoretical learning. Through this method, students are encouraged to analyze problems deeply, provide critical responses, and discover solutions, thereby significantly enriching their learning experiences. This model was originally developed by John Dewey and involves the active participation of all students in the learning process, both individually and collaboratively. PjBL is a pedagogical approach that emphasizes learning through the completion of real-world projects. These projects require students' active involvement throughout the entire learning process. Students are presented with complex problems or questions that require in-depth investigation and creative solutions. PjBL projects often integrate multiple disciplines, allowing students to apply various concepts and skills in meaningful and relevant contexts. In addition, PjBL promotes collaboration among students, which is essential for developing strong social and communication skills (Didik, 2023).

Creative thinking skills involve the ability to generate solutions when solving problems, enabling individuals to create something new. Through creative thinking, students can view the world from multiple perspectives, which ultimately helps them find innovative solutions

to real-world problems. On the other hand, critical thinking is a cognitive aspect that is useful for identifying problems, finding solutions, and making logically reasoned decisions to resolve those problems. Therefore, critical thinking skills are essential for developing cognition and retaining information effectively. Unfortunately, low levels of creative and critical thinking skills are often caused by science learning activities that are still limited to lecture-based methods, discussions, and teacher-centered laboratory activities. This condition reinforces the need for the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model, which has great potential to enhance students' creativity and critical thinking skills. Through PjBL, students are given the freedom to think beyond conventional boundaries, design, and implement their ideas, thereby increasing their confidence in their creative abilities (Fitriana, 2024).

Formulation of the problem

The problem formulation in this article focuses on how the implementation of the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model can develop students' critical thinking skills through project-centered learning activities. This article examines which aspects of PjBL contribute to the improvement of students' analytical and problem-solving abilities. It also addresses who plays a role in supporting the effectiveness of this model, when PjBL strategies are most appropriately implemented in the learning process, where project activities can be carried out to provide meaningful learning experiences, why PjBL is considered relevant for developing 21st-century skills—particularly critical thinking—and how the implementation mechanisms of PjBL encourage students to observe, evaluate, and draw logical conclusions (Email et al., 2014).

Method

The method used in this study is a literature review. This research aims to examine the effect of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) on students' critical thinking skills. The reference sources are drawn from researchers whose articles were analyzed. Data were collected from publications published between 2017 and 2022. The literature search was conducted using the ERIC, Harzing Publish or Perish, and Google Scholar databases. PjBL was examined because this model is believed to be effective in improving critical thinking skills. The study was carried out through several stages, including determining the research objectives, selecting databases, establishing the keyword "Project-Based Learning," screening articles based on inclusion criteria, and conducting content analysis to synthesize findings from previous studies.

The review of critical thinking skills covers several aspects. First, the types of skills analyzed. Second, the students who served as subjects in the discussed articles. Third, when critical thinking skills emerged during the learning process. Fourth, where these skills were applied within the educational contexts examined. Fifth, why these skills are important for helping students identify and solve problems logically. Finally, how these skills develop through the implementation of PjBL across the various studies analyzed in this review (Didik, 2023).

Results

No.	Article Source	Research Focus	Main Findings Related to PjBL	Example	Impact on Critical Thinking
1	National Journal (<i>Indonesian Journal of Science Education – “Implementation of PjBL in Science Learning to Improve Students’ Analysis Skills”</i>)	Implementation of PjBL in science and social studies learning	PjBL increases students’ active engagement through structured project activities	Science students create a mini ecosystem model and analyze factors affecting its balance	Students demonstrate improved ability to analyze and evaluate information
2	ERIC Database	Effectiveness of PjBL compared to conventional methods	PjBL provides greater opportunities for exploration and collaboration	Students design solutions to reduce plastic waste at school and present their results	A significant improvement occurs in problem-solving and critical reasoning skills
3	Harzing Publish or Perish	Project design in PjBL	Relevant and contextual projects increase learning motivation	Students create a healthy food business proposal and write reflections on marketing strategies	The reflection process strengthens students’ synthesis and evaluation skills
4	Google Scholar (<i>International Journal of Digital Learning – “Online PjBL to Enhance Inquiry Skills in Virtual Classrooms”</i>)	PjBL in digital/online learning	Technological support makes projects more flexible and interactive	Students create digital infographics on environmental issues after comparing online data	Critical thinking improves through digital-based investigative activities

5	International Journal (<i>Journal of Innovative Teaching and Learning</i> – “The Role of Teacher Scaffolding in Successful PjBL Implementation”)	Teacher’s role in PjBL	Teachers act as facilitators who guide students progressively	Teachers provide guiding questions, such as “What evidence supports your conclusion?”	Improvement in critical thinking is influenced by scaffolding and intensive feedback
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Discussion

The articles included in this literature review were required to meet several specific criteria. First, the articles had to be available in either English or Indonesian with free full-text access. Second, there had to be alignment between the article titles and contents and the research objectives. Third, the articles had to be published within the period from 2017 to 2022. The results of the literature analysis indicate that the implementation of the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model in Biology instruction has a positive impact on improving students’ critical thinking skills. All review results are presented in tabular form, containing a unique article code, the full article title, and a summary of the review findings for each article (Sugiharyanti, 2022).

Similarly, the articles included in this literature review were required to meet the same criteria: availability in English or Indonesian with free full-text access, relevance of titles and content to the research objectives, and publication between 2017 and 2022. The findings consistently show that the application of the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model in Biology learning positively influences the enhancement of students’ critical thinking skills. The results of the review are also presented in a table consisting of unique article codes, complete article titles, and summaries of the review results for each article (Didik, 2023).

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) has been proven to enhance learners’ abilities to think critically, creatively, and to become competent problem solvers. Satria and Muntaha (2021) emphasize that PjBL is flexible, allowing its implementation to be adapted to various subject matters. This flexibility depends on teachers’ creativity in setting appropriate learning objectives. Furthermore, PjBL is well suited to empowering learners, as it represents an ideal pedagogical approach in which students are actively engaged in all learning activities. Riskayanti (2021) adds that this model is effective in developing students’ 4C skills—Critical Thinking, Communication, Collaboration, and Creativity (Mulyanti et al., 2024).

Conclusion

Based on the discussion of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) and its relationship with the development of critical thinking skills, it can be concluded that PjBL is a relevant and effective learning model for addressing the demands of 21st-century education. Through the

implementation of authentic projects that position teachers as facilitators and students as active participants, PjBL provides learners with opportunities to explore problems, analyze information, and generate creative solutions. This approach not only addresses the 5W1H aspects in the implementation of learning strategies, but also fulfills the 5W1H elements in the process of developing critical thinking skills, including what needs to be analyzed, who is involved in problem solving, when and where evaluation takes place, why critical thinking skills are necessary, and how the strategy is systematically implemented. Therefore, PjBL is able to provide meaningful and sustainable learning experiences while preparing students to think more reflectively, logically, and independently in facing various academic challenges and real-life situations.

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